

Ustacystis waldsteiniae, a remarkable smut fungus (*Ustilaginomycetes*)

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Abstract. An historical account is given of the smut fungus, *Ustacystis waldsteiniae*, which is parasitic on members of *Rosaceae*. This is followed by a short characterisation of the unispecific genus *Ustacystis*, and a detailed, illustrated description of *U. waldsteiniae*. Synonyms of the genus and species, host plant range and geographic distribution are also provided.

Key words: *Geum*, plant parasite, *Rosaceae*, smut fungi, *Urocystidaceae*, *Ustacystis*, *U. waldsteiniae*, *Waldsteinia*

Introduction. History

A smut fungus that produced unusual sori and spores on the leaves of *Waldsteinia fragarioides* (*Rosaceae*), was collected by C.L. Shear in USA, New York State, Albany Co., Alcove, in June, 1892. It was described by the eminent American mycologist, Charles Horton Peck, and published under the name *Urocystis waldsteiniae*. Regarding the generic name, Peck (1893: 112) wrote: “This species is apparently closest allied to *U. filipendulae*. It seems to connect *Urocystis* with *Thecaphora* and to be ambiguous between these two genera. When there are but three spores in a glomerule the central one is usually larger than the others.” From this comment, it seems that the generic placement of this fungus was to some extent uncertain for Peck. Indeed, Peck’s feelings were justified later, but for different reasons.

The rich original collection of Shear was divided, and isotypes were distributed in the following exsiccatae: Shear, N.Y. fgi. no. 86, Ellis & Ev., N. Amer. fgi. no. 2983, and Ellis & Ev., Fgi. Columb. no. 137. Shear repeatedly collected rich material of this fungus, on the same host plant, from the same locality. Topotypes, collected in May 1893, were distributed in Seymour & Earle, Econ. fgi., Suppl. C. no. 62, and in US Dept. Agricult., Plant Industry, Pathological Collections no. 46. Topotypes collected on 14.VI.1893 were distributed in Rabenh., Fgi. eur. no. 4011, under the name *Ustilago waldsteiniae* (Peck) Pazschke. On the label, Pazschke wrote: “Obs.: Meines Erachtens kann dieser Pilz weder zu *Urocystis*, noch zu *Thecaphora* gestellt werden, da die Sporen sämtlich

gleichgestaltet sind und nur anfangs zusammenhängen. Aeltere Sporenlager enthalten nur noch sehr wenige zusammenhängende Sporen.” [In my opinion, this fungus can neither be included in *Urocystis* nor in *Thecaphora*, because all spores are of the same kind, and only at the beginning they are connected. Older sori contain only very few connected spores]. This fungus was subsequently collected on the same host plant, in many places in the USA and Canada. A collection by J.J. Davis, on 12.VI.1893 from Three Lakes (Wisconsin), was distributed in Sydow, Ust. no. 248 (as *Urocystis waldsteiniae*). The fungus was found also on the closely related host genus *Geum* (see also next paragraph), and distributed in Ellis & Ev., Fgi. Columb. no. 1595, *G. ciliatum*, USA, Washington, Waitsburg, 7.V.1900, coll. R.M. Horner (BPI 182 684, 183097, HUV 16 158!). Further host plants in the BPI list (specimens not checked) are *Geum triflorum* (USA, Montana, Maxville, leg. J.A. Hughes, 2.VII.1917, BPI 183 098), *Potentilla* sp.(?), (Canada, Saskatchewan, Indian Head, 1917?, coll. O.P. Cowan, det. G.P. Clinton, BPI 182 687), *Sieversia triflora* (= *Geum triflorum*; Canada, Manitoba, Treesbank, 3.VI.1919, coll. E. Griddle, BPI 182 688; Saskatchewan, Saskatoon, coll. W.P. Fraser, BPI 183 100). All these host genera are closely related and their species were not rarely transferred from one genus to another.

Ellis & Everhart (1900: 572) described a new smut species, *Urocystis gei* Ellis & Ev., on *Geum ciliatum*, USA, Washington, Waitsburg, 7.V.1900, R.M. Horner 1430. Clinton (1902: 129) considered that *Urocystis gei* is a synonym of *Urocystis waldsteiniae*.

Liro (1922: 90), according to the generic concept of *Urocystis* at that time, proposed the new combination *Tuburcinia waldsteiniae* (Peck) Liro. However, *Urocystis* Rabenh. ex Fuckel (1870: 41) was conserved against *Tuburcinia* Fries (1832: 439) and consequently Liro's name was abandoned.

Clinton (1904: 447–448) wrote: “This fungus [*Urocystis waldsteiniae*] is peculiar in that while it has the general aspect of an *Urocystis* its position under this genus is somewhat doubtful since it lacks the peripheral layer of sterile cells. Neither does it seem to be a true *Ustilago*, as considered by Pazschke, since the spores adhere somewhat in pairs or small groups. . . . Those spores that adhere in pairs have the appearance of *Schizonella*. Often some of the largest spores appear to be sterile cells merely.” Clinton concludes that “The generic position of this species is unsettled, but is placed here (i.e. in *Urocystis*) until further study determines its place.” Furthermore, Clinton (1904: 448, footnote) wrote: “Since the above was written the writer has been informed by Dr. Thom that he has succeeded in germinating the spores and the germination is of the *Ustilago* rather than of the *Urocystis* type. This makes the species come under the former genus.”

Hanson & Atkinson (1938) germinated the spores and studied the cytology of *Urocystis waldsteiniae*. They demonstrated that the haplophase has been almost eliminated. “The fusion nucleus apparently undergoes meiosis in the chlamydo-spore, as very young promycelia are binucleate and all subsequent vegetative development is dicaryotic.”

Zundel (1945a), during the preparation of his monograph, *The Ustilaginales of the world* (1953), studied all literature of the great classics of descriptive mycology, including those mentioned above, as well as all available specimens. He decided that this much confused fungus belonged to an undescribed genus of the family *Ustilaginaceae*, and proposed the name *Whetzelia* Zundel. Unfortunately, the name was already occupied by *Whetzelia* Chardón & Toro. Therefore, Zundel (1945b: 796) renamed his genus *Whetzelia* as *Ustacystis*.

Whereas *Ustacystis waldsteiniae* was rather often collected in Canada and USA but never outside North America until 1934, when Y. Tochinai & Tokunaga collected it on a new host plant species, *Waldsteinia sibirica* (= *W. ternata*), in Japan, Ishikari Prov., Mt. Taisetsu (SAPA!), and published later by Kakishima (1982: 76). In April 1936, A. Borza & J. Zapetalek collected it on an additional new host, *Waldsteinia geoides*, in “Siebenbürgen, Visa bei Cluj” [= Transylvania, Vișea, near Cluj-Napoca, Romania]. This collection, distributed in Petrak, Mycoth. generalis no. 394 (as *Tuburcinia waldsteiniae*) was not known to Săvulescu (1957). It was first published in Vánky (1985: 188). An attempt to find this smut again in May 1965 failed, because of deforestation and habitat destruction the host plant disappeared. Only on 21.V.1987 did I succeed in finding it in Hungary, comit. Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén, close to the village Aggtelek, also on *Waldsteinia geoides*. The rich collection was distributed in Vánky, Ustil. no. 629 (comp. Vánky 1987: 10). Living, smutted plants were successfully transferred to two localities in Tübingen, Germany, in shady places, beneath mixed trees and bushes where they grow and spread. Here, the

Fig. 1. Infected *Waldsteinia geoides* with sori of *Ustacystis waldsteiniae* on the leaves (from Hungary, in Vánky, *Ust. exs.* no. 628). Habit. Bar = 1 cm

smut was observed during 21 years, and detailed studies were carried out on these specimens. Bauer *et al.* (1995a, b) described and illustrated the septal pore apparatus and the cellular interaction of *Ustacystis waldsteiniae*. They demonstrated that *Ustacystis* is similar to *Urocystis*, in having haustoria and simple septal pores with membrane caps and two non-membranous plates closing the pore. Based on ultrastructural markers, a new order, *Urocystidales* R. Bauer & Oberw. (as ‘*Urocystales*’) was described (Bauer *et al.* 1997). Further molecular phylogenetic analyses lead Begerow *et al.* (1998) to propose a new family, *Urocystidaceae* Begerow *et al.* (as ‘*Urocystaceae*’), which includes *Urocystis* Rabenh. ex Fuckel, *Ustacystis* Zundel, *Flamingomyces* R. Bauer *et al.*, *Melanustilospora* Denchev, *Mundkurella* Thirum., and *Vankya* Ershad.

The unique spore germination of *Ustacystis waldsteiniae* (see below) was studied, described and illustrated i.a. by Hanson & Atkinson (1938), Ingold (1992) and Vánky (1994). According to the recent classificatory system of the smut fungi, *Ustacystis* belongs to the fam. *Urocystidaceae*, ord. *Urocystidales*, cl. *Ustilaginomycetes*, subphylum *Ustilaginomycotina*, phylum *Basidiomycota*.

Figs 2–3. Details of sori of *Ustacystis waldsteiniae* on leaves of *Waldsteinia geoides* (from the author's garden). Fig. 4. A semi-thin, stained transversal section of a very young sorus of *Ustacystis waldsteiniae* from a leaf of *Waldsteinia geoides* (Vánky, *Ust. exs.* no. 628). Note the read coloured mass of sporogenous hyphae, very close to the upper, epiphyllous epidermis, within a circle of a leaf vein. Bar = 100 μ m

Materials and methods

Sorus structure, spore ball and spore characteristics were studied using living material or dried herbarium specimens. For microscopic studies of the soral characters, freshly collected leaves with young, unopened sori were fixed in 2 % glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M Na-cacodylate buffer at pH 7.2 for several days. After six transfers in 0.1 M Na-cacodylate buffer, the material was postfixed in 1 % osmiumtetroxide in the same buffer for 1 h in the dark, washed in distilled water, and

stained in 1 % aqueous uranyl acetate for 1 h in the dark. After five washes in distilled water, the material was dehydrated in acetone series, embedded in Spurr's plastic and sectioned with a diamond knife. Semi-thin sections were stained with new fuchsin and crystal violet, mounted in "Entellan" and studied in a light microscope. For light microscopy (LM) spore balls and spores were suspended in a small droplet of lactophenol, covered with a cover glass, gently heated to boiling point to rehydrate the spores and eliminate air bubbles from the preparation, and studied at 1000 \times magnification. For

Figs 5–6. Spore balls and spores of *Ustacystis waldsteiniae* on *Waldsteinia geoides* in LM and in SEM (Vánky, *Ust.* exs. no. 628). Bars = 10 μ m and 5 μ m, respectively

scanning electron microscopy (SEM), spores were placed on double-sided adhesive tape, mounted on a specimen stub, sputter-coated with gold-palladium, *ca* 20 nm, and examined in a SEM at 10 kV. Germination of freshly collected spores was obtained on water agar, at room temp., in a few days.

Results

Based on own observations and on literature data, this curious smut fungus can be described and illustrated as follows:

Ustacystis Zundel, 1945b: 796.

Whetzelia Zundel, 1945a: 371, later homonym, not Chardón & Toro, 1934 (a genus of *Dothideaceae*, *Ascomycota*).

Sori in leaves of plants in *Rosaceae*, following the veins, swollen, at first covered by a peridium which at maturity splits longitudinally exposing the semi-agglutinated, blackish brown spore mass. **Spores** single, in pairs, or in indefinite, loose, few-spored balls. No sterile cells. **Spore germination**: two-celled basidia produce large, dikaryotic basidiospores, dikaryotic hyphae, or both, usually one per basidial cell, either laterally or one laterally and one terminally. **Host-parasite interaction** by haustoria. **Septal pore** simple with membrane caps and two non-membranous plates closing the pore. **Type**: *U. waldsteiniae*.

Ustacystis waldsteiniae (C.H. Peck) G.L. Zundel, 1945b: 796.

Urocystis waldsteiniae Peck, 1893: 112. — *Ustilago waldsteiniae* (Peck) Pazschke, in Rabenhorst, Fgi. eur. no.

4011, 1895. — *Tubercinia waldsteiniae* (Peck) Liro, 1922: 90. — *Whetzelia waldsteiniae* (Peck) Zundel, 1945a: 372. — Type on *Waldsteinia fragarioides*, USA, New York, Albany Co., Alcove, June 1892, C.L. Shear; isotypes in Ellis & Ev., N. Amer. fgi. no. 2983, HUV 9075!, in Shear, N.Y. fgi. no. 86, HUV 5222!, in Ellis & Ev., Fgi. Columb. no. 137, HUV 16157(!).

Urocystis gei Ellis & Everhart, 1900: 572. — *Ustacystis gei* (Ellis & Everh.) H. Zogg, 1986: 131. — Type on *Geum ciliatum* (= *G. triflorum* var. *ciliatum*), USA, Washington, Waitesburg, 7 May 1900, R.M. Horner, 1430 (syn. by Clinton 1902: 129).

Sori (Figs 1–4) in leaves, epiphyllous, following the veins, oval, linear or bifurcate, Y-shaped, swollen, initially covered by a greyish peridium formed of host tissue, which at maturity splits longitudinally exposing the rather agglutinated, reddish brown spore mass. Infection systemic, appearing each season on the same plant. Infected plants flower normally. **Spores** (Figs 5–6) varying in shape, size, colour and wall-thickness, globose, subglobose, hemispheric, oblong or polyhedral to rather irregular, 7–12 (–15) \times 9–15 (–18) μ m, single, in pairs or adherent in groups of 3 or more, forming loose spore balls, reddish brown, with sparsely situated, low, rounded, hyaline warts. **Sterile cells** absent. **Spore germination** (Figs 7–8; Hanson & Atkinson 1938: 8; Ingold 1992: 161–166, Figs 18–27; Vánky 1994: 343–344, fig. C) results in two-celled basidia (occasionally two, one-celled basidia per spore) producing basidiospores, hyphae, or both, usually one per basidial cell, either laterally or one laterally and one terminally. Basidiospores long-ellipsoidal or subfusiform, very large, measuring 3.5–4.5

Figs 7–8. Germinating spores of *Ustacystis waldsteiniae* on *Waldsteinia geoides*, on water agar, at room temp., in 6 days (Vánky, *Ust.* exs. no. 628). Bars = 10 μ m

$\times 24\text{--}32$ μ m, hyaline. They have never been observed to bud, but germinate from one or both ends, or occasionally from the side. The haplophase has been almost eliminated; basidial cells and subsequent vegetative development being dikaryotic.

On *Rosaceae*: *Geum triflorum* Pursh (*Sieversia triflora* (Pursh) R.Br.), *G. triflorum* var. *ciliatum* (Pursh) Fassett (*G. ciliatum* Pursh), *Waldsteinia fragarioides* (Michx.) Tratt., *W. geoides* Willd., *W. ternata* (Steph.) Fritsch (*W. sibirica* Tratt.).

Distribution: Europe (Hungary, Germany, Romania), E. Asia (Japan), N. America (Canada, USA).

The following observations of two infected *Waldsteinia geoides* populations in Tübingen, Germany (namely in the Botanical Garden and in the author's garden, with both populations originating from Hungary), were made over 21 years:

1. The infection is systemic; infected plants produce diseased leaves year after year.

2. Infected plants produce both infected and healthy new plants at the end of shorter or longer stolons.

3. In spring, the first 1–3 smaller leaves of the infected plants have no sori, only the following, well-developed 2–4 leaves appear diseased, followed by production of healthy leaves and development of normal inflorescence.

4. Plants growing in shadier places were more heavily infected than those exposed to more sunlight. Some diseased

plants growing in places exposed to much sunlight, became apparently healthy, no longer producing smutted leaves.

5. In some years the infection was more expressed than in others, probably depending on climatic conditions.

6. *Ustacystis waldsteiniae* does not kill the host plant but coexists with its host.

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